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Revisión del estado del arte y diseño
inicial de la integración público-privada
en 6GSMART
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3 List of Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5 th Generation
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6 th Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet Of Things Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
CORC	Continuum ORChestrator
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
E2E	End-to-End
EU/UE	European Union
EUCEI	EU Cloud Edge IoT
FENS	Factory Edge Network Service
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDC	Google Distributed Cloud
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSMA	GSM (Groupe Spéciale Mobile) Association
I4.0	Industry 4.0
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IIoT	Industrial Internet Of Things
IT	Information Technology
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LST&P	Large Scale Trials and Pilots
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
ML	Machine Learning
NPN	Non-Public Networks
NSaaS	Network Slicing as a Service
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OP	Operator Platform
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
PLC	Programmable Logic Controllers
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDN	Software Define Networks
SDO	Standards Developing Organizations
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SNS JU	Software Networks & Services Joint Undertaking
SSID	Service Set Identifier
TAC	Tracking Area Code
UN	United Nations

UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
US	United States
VM	Virtual Machine
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
WG	Working Group
XR	Extended Reality

4 Executive Summary

6GSMART-ICC Project studies the application of 6G in the manufacturing area, with a focus on the orchestration of the cloud-continuum in industrial use cases that leverage the integration of resources in the public and private domains. The project is framed under the *Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia* of the Spanish Government that channels the *Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)* funding of *NextGenerationEU*.

The new technologies introduced in 5G networks, such as Network Function Virtualization, Multi-access Edge Computing and Software Defined Networks have changed the ecosystem and the way telco services are consumed from general public to vertical industries like manufacturing. There are, however, new challenges introduced in the management of the increased availability of hyper-distributed computing resources at different tiers of the network. This availability enables application developers to design innovative solutions that leverage the new service offering, but a gap exists between the developers focused on the challenges of the vertical specific solutions and the complexities of next generation networks. The upcoming 6G technology is required to take on this challenge and facilitate the interaction of vertical applications with 6G networks.

Vertical applications that require integrated deployments across hybrid clouds that extend across the public and private domains demand orchestration mechanisms that facilitate this integration through an abstraction that enables translation between the telco and vertical languages.

This document first presents a study of the State of the Art, in particular the point of view organizations such as the GSMA and the offering of cloud infrastructure providers like AWS, Azure or GCP. Then, a system architecture that takes on the challenges of Cloud Continuum orchestration between public and private domains from the perspective of application developers is described with a specific focus on highlighting the public-private integration considerations.

5 Introduction

This document provides a report on the State-of-the-Art review on the Public-private integration across the Cloud Continuum concept and the considerations for large scale implementation of hyper-distributed applications from the perspective of application developers and presents a preliminary system architecture design of a Cloud Continuum orchestration framework.

This document is the results of project task *6GSMART-SP1-L2-T2.1.2: Revisión del estado del arte y principios de diseño de redes público-privadas, bajo la perspectiva de un desarrollador de tecnologías cloud* described in the project's execution plan. The work reported on this document serves as a basis of work towards a final architecture that will be reported on deliverables *6GSMART P1-P1-D1.2 "Diseño final y evaluación del cloud continuo de 6GSMART"* and *6GSMART P2-P1-D2.2 "Diseño final y evaluación de la solución para integración de redes públicas y privadas en 6GSMART"*.

5.1 Objectives

The first objective of this document is to present a review on the Public-Private integration aspects around the Cloud Continuum concept, standardization initiatives like the GSMA Operator Platform and solutions offered by public cloud providers to integrate other domain resources with their offerings.

Furthermore, based on the results of this State of the Art and technological review reported, the second objective is to highlight those aspects of the preliminary system architecture presented in D1.1 that are relevant and enable this integration into hybrid cloud-continuum.

6 State of the Art Review

In recent years, the proliferation of cloud computing and the advent of 5G technology have revolutionized the digital landscape, enabling unprecedented connectivity and computing capabilities. As we approach the next generation of wireless communication, 6G, the integration of multiple cloud services This section delves into the state of the art regarding the integration of the resources of these clouds into a cloud continuum, focusing on the perspective of cloud application developers.

Deliverable 6GSMART P1-P1-D1.1 *Revisión del estado del arte y diseño inicial del cloud continuo de 6GSMART* state of the art section focuses on exploring the concept of cloud-continuum and the most relevant research initiatives around the topic. This document, instead, focuses on the relevance of an integration between public and private domains, which could be considered a critical component of the cloud continuum, especially in the current ecosystem where public cloud providers play a role that is becoming more and more the standard of IT infrastructure. There are, however, areas such as the privacy of the data or use cases where ultra-low latencies and reliability are required, for example in industrial scenarios, which may indicate the necessity for a portion of private infrastructure to be integrated with more general and cost-effective resources like the ones provided by public clouds.

In this context, there is a third leg that plays a role (although arguably from the same side of the public providers) which is that of the Telco operators. Of course, they are the ones offering the connectivity and access to the computing resources, either private or public. The following subsection takes a look at the proposal from GSMA's Operator Platform as a reference for the implantation of means of interaction between enterprises and telco networks. Also, we look at different offerings from the most relevant hyperscalers to provide control over clusters distributed across public and private administrative domains.

6.1 Seamless inter-domain resource orchestration in public-private network scenarios

The GSMA Operator platform aims to provide a reference architecture for the integration between Telco operator networks and enterprises. The *Operator Platform Telco Edge Requirements*¹ Permanent Reference Document identifies and establishes a set of requirements, building blocks, interfaces and interactions with and within these platforms with the aim to cover existing standardization gaps and guide industry ecosystem, including operators, network equipment and software providers and service providers and SDOs and Open Source communities in the exposure and consumption of network capabilities with a focus on edge computing use cases, in an adaptable manner making the proposal future proof for potential new applications as well as fit into existing network architectures.

¹ <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/GSMA-OPG-Telco-Edge-Requirements-2021.pdf>

The main high-level requirements outlined by the report are, starting from the general requirements, the Operator platform shall:

- Expose network capabilities and resources to users and applications.
- Provide a single instance of the platform that represents and allows the management of all the operators' resources and capabilities.
- Provide isolated multitenancy capabilities.
- Use the commonly defined interfaces to provide the exposure.

In this work we will focus on the perspective of application providers and users, which will exploit the capabilities and resources offered by the platform. In this regard, GSMA identifies the following requirements that the Operator Platform shall meet from the perspective of the application providers:

- Enable a single interface for the application developers to deploy edge applications serving multiple operators (requires federation of platforms across operators)
- Through this interface, simplify the deployment of applications designed for public cloud providers.
- The capability to reserve resources to guarantee availability to the application provider.
- Hide the complexity inherent to 5G and beyond networks to the application provider.
- Clearly separate the responsibilities, detail awareness and concerns between Application provider and Network provider.
- Provide the Application provider with inter-networks (where the application is deployed) monitoring capabilities.
- Provide interconnection capabilities that enable interfacing between the application services deployed inside and outside the network.
- Provide a secure, private, trusted and regulation compliance data storage capabilities.
- Enable VM-based and Containerized applications.
- Provide network services exposure to applications.

From the point of view of the End-Users, the platform shall allow access to edge applications in a seamless and secure manner and enable device mobility across networks.

Focusing on the edge capabilities, the requirements from the platform are outlined as the capability to expose computing and storage resources for deployment of applications and the enablement of low latency communication between services that are deployed across multiple operator networks in the same area. As mentioned above, the ability to reserve resources for an application, manage its lifecycle, in a mobile scenario while maintaining the security and data privacy is key in the definition of the platform.

Other considerations, like roaming scenarios are also considered but will be more detailed in future versions of the document.

The proposed platform architecture defines a series of roles that the platform enacts as a coordinator between multiple actors and a series of interfaces that are used to communicate to and from the platform to fulfil the mentioned requirements.

The main roles in this architecture that will materialize into different modules are:

- The **Capability Exposure Role** which enables features to the Application provider such as Application Onboarding, Lifecycle management and edge-cloud resource exposure.
- The **Service Resource Manager Role** which communicates with the user equipment, mobile network and cloud resources manager for maintaining the resource catalogue that the previous role exposes, orchestrating the workloads and setting up the network data-plane, triggering lifecycle operations on the application-based UE interactions.
- The **Federation Manager Role**, in charge of enabling the interaction of the platform with other instances through an east-west interface to discover their services, and manage the applications lifecycle across, increasing the geographical availability of the services.

Figure 1. OP Roles and Interfaces Reference Architecture²

This architecture is requirements has developed into GSMA Open Gateway³ which helps application developers access the capabilities of 5G and Beyond networks across a federated mesh of operator's networks via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). This requires the design and development interfaces open to third parties that have extensive reach, are integrable into the rich existing development environments in use by application developers currently, help ease the adoption by simplification of complexities and at the same time are trustable and provide a top level of data security and privacy to application developers.

These APIs are being developed under CAMARA⁴ Open-Source project under the umbrella of the Linux Foundation. The objective of this project is to create user-friendly APIs that help developers, without intensive telco expertise, enhance their applications with capabilities from the Network.

² <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/GSMA-Operator-Platform-Proposal-Oct-2020.pdf>

³ <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/gsma-open-gateway/>

⁴ <https://camaraproject.org/>

The main scenario⁵ that the Open Gateway considers centres around three roles, the **consumer**, application developer that consumes the APIs, the **operators** that serve the capabilities of the network through the CAMARA interfaces, and the potential **aggregators**, such as hyperscalers, that may optionally consume the APIs and enhance the capabilities offered with their own services. This scenario allows for the application developers to directly consume the APIs from an operator portal or through an aggregator, depending on his requirements and the services offered.

Figure 2. Different relationship models for Open Gateway⁶

This initiative enables hyperscalers to enhance their services over telco networks with ease for the developers. The main hyperscalers in the market (AWS, Azure and GCP) have already got service offerings in their catalogue that enable the leveraging of Telco networks, but only in a limited way until now.

AWS Wavelength⁷ service enables the deployment of user applications including computing instances and storage inside the operator's network and connect them and other loads running on the cloud via Virtual Private Cloud (VPC) subnets and carrier gateways that interconnect with the telco network. A small number of networks and regions is supported at the moment in UK, US, Canada, Japan and South Korea but it is expected these locations to be extended as adoption grows.

⁵ <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/The-Ecosystem-for-Open-Gateway-NaaS-API-development.pdf>

⁶ <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/The-Ecosystem-for-Open-Gateway-NaaS-API-development.pdf>

⁷ <https://aws.amazon.com/wavelength/>

Figure 3. AWS Wavelength⁷

Similarly, Azure Edge Zones⁸ enables the application developers to leverage computing resources placed at the telco edge through low-latency links. One of the limitations of this service is that agreements and integrated deployments are required with each telco network and only AT&T operator (in the US) is supported at this moment.

Figure 4. Service offerings for Azure public MEC⁹

In the case of GCP, Google Distributed Cloud (GDC) Edge focuses on providing the network operators with a set of tools to deploy 5G MEC, placing them first, instead of the users that want to deploy their loads at the telco edge. This strategy is different to that of Microsoft and AWS. GCP proposes Anthos¹⁰ service to enable the operator to manage the created environment that expands multiple clusters across different providers and on-prem.

⁸ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/architecture/example-scenario/hybrid/public-multi-access-edge-compute-deployment>

⁹ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/public-multi-access-edge-compute-mec/overview>

¹⁰ <https://cloud.google.com/anthos/docs/concepts/overview>

Figure 5. Google Cloud Anthos basics¹⁰

7 Preliminary System Architecture Review

This section, starting from the basis of D1.1¹¹, where the system architecture that will enable the orchestration of applications across the cloud-continuum is described, highlights the specific requirements and architectural components that play a role in the public-private integration. The focus on this deliverable is to describe the general functionality of the orchestrator focusing on its capability to manage the public-private integration in the cloud-continuum.

7.1 High-level requirements

This section highlights from the requirements in D1.1¹¹, those that have a special focus on the public-private domains integration. For the sake of readability, the complete list of requirements (including the ones described here) is presented in D1.1¹¹. This section contains only the specific requirements that have a role to play in the public-private integration challenge.

In relation to the applications management, the system should:

- Enable the deployment of the different components of an application to be deployed across multiple computing resources, expanding across multiple domains.
- Monitor metrics and KPIs related to the deployed applications.

In relation to the management of the computing infrastructure, the system should:

- Integrate computing resources across multiple domains.
- Integrate computing resources from multiple providers.
- Integrate computing resources from public (hyperscalers) and private domains (on-prem).
- Abstract the multi-domain, network, and connectivity complexities between the application's internal components.
- Configure and provision computing resources remotely.
- Monitor metrics and logs related to the infrastructure utilization, performance and health, and implement the necessary alerting mechanisms for administrators.

In relation to the management of inter-domain connectivity, the system should:

- Be able to request the establishment of connectivity from the telco operator platforms based on the application requirements.

In relation to security and data management, the system should:

- Ensure the data privacy and security within the deployed applications, across the computing infrastructure, and through the communications inter-domain.

¹¹ 6GSMART P1-P1-D1.1

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7.2 Concept and General Architecture

This section describes the concept and general architecture of the continuum orchestration system that will enable users to deploy end-to-end applications across computing resources distributed in multiple locations of the continuum, extending to cloud, edge and extreme edge locations and leveraging the connectivity services provided by 6G networks. **CORC**, short for **C**ontinuum-**OR**chestrator, enables the centralized orchestration of applications across a hybrid (public-private) cloud-continuum. It unifies and simplifies the deployment of applications that expand across multiple domains and benefits from the services provided by the next generation 6G networks. This section highlights the specific aspects of the full architecture described in D1.1¹¹ that are relevant to the public-private integration challenge.

Figure 6 below depicts a graphical representation of the modular CORC architecture. Each of the modules represents a specific functionality extracted from the set of high-level requirements described in D1.1¹¹.

Figure 6. Preliminary CORC General Architecture

The concept of the CORC is based on two different domains: the private vertical, including the application developer role, the system administrator manages the CORC and the users of the applications, the public telco & cloud providers domain.

One of the two main goals of the architecture (the other one being the enablement of the cloud-continuum orchestration) is to enable enterprises to integrate their private IT resources with those IT and Telco resources offered by public service providers to assist in tackling business-specific challenges.

In this architecture, the CORC plays the role of the consumer as per the roles identified by GSMA's Operator Platform (Figure 2). The relationships of the CORC with each of the providers could be implemented as a one-to-one relationship with either hyperscalers or telco providers, or through aggregation of resources via hyperscalers as envisioned by GSMA, depending on the service offerings of each of them.

Figure 7. CORC Role and relationships

Via this scheme, the CORC allows the user to request and manage infrastructure from public providers such as AWS, Azure or GCP, join existing private infrastructure at the edge and discover resources that connect to the infrastructure from the Access side using the services provided by a telco operator. CORC provides the coordination across this continuum.

CORC interface enables the user to manage 4 types of resources, namely Zones, Clusters and Providers and Applications:

- **Zone:** Zones are conceived as a combination of geographic and network locations with the aim of forming characterized groups of resources and providing the CORC with information about what tier of the cloud-continuum the resources available in such zone are considered as in direct relation with the topological location they are placed in within the operator's network. Based on this definition, the main characteristics of each zone can be established as:
 - Each zone contains information about a specific point of presence within an operator's network.
 - Each zone can be categorized as one of the following types: ExtremeEdge, Edge or Cloud zones.
 - The Cloud zone type is the default zone type when a zone is not of type Edge or Extreme Edge. This means that a zone without a specific operator's point of presence is of type cloud.
 - An Edge zone is specially characterized by the information of the operator's Network that provides Access to it such as CellId, TAC, SSID, etc... This zone type is characterized by being statically mapped to that access network information.
 - Instances of both Cloud and Edge zones maintain a list of computing resources clusters available in the zone.
 - An Extreme Edge zone represents a group of UEs with computing capabilities available and is characterized by their UE ids, their geographic location (i.e., GPS coordinates) and the information of the

Access Network that provides service to them. In this instance, however, the network information is of dynamic nature but common across devices. This means an Extreme Edge access network information can be changed, mapping the behaviour of device mobility.

- Instances of Extreme Edge zones dynamically group devices that are discovered in the zone into a single cluster of resources.
- **Computing Resources Clusters:** Each of the defined zones can be tied to one or several instances of the logical concept of Computing Resources Cluster that represents instances of groups of clustered computing resources such as Kubernetes or K3s clusters. Existing clusters in the infrastructure can be onboarded to the platform by providing the necessary detailed information about its characteristics and credentials to manage and operate it and be associated to a specific zone with an indication of which is the provider of each cluster. A special case of Computing Resources Clusters would be those at the Extreme Edge. These clusters will be enabled by the automated discovery of devices in the network and management, being incorporated to the clusters as computing nodes while available in the network and removed when they are no longer available, due to disconnection or mobility into another zone.
- **Computing Resources Clusters Provider:** New clusters can be created and managed through the platform provided that the necessary provider API information and credentials have been provided. Each instance holds the information about the provider details, including credentials and API endpoints to interface with a provider. A provider can be PrivateOnPrem or PublicCloud.
 - PrivateOnPrem indicates that the cluster is provided privately by the vertical entity IT services.
 - PublicCloud indicates that the cluster is provided by a public cloud infrastructure provider such as AWS, Azure or GCP.
- **Telco Network Provider:** Telco network providers facilitate the underlying connectivity between zones in the continuum. When adding a zone to the continuum, specific information regarding the network point of presence serving the clusters in the zone is provided, creating a tight coupling between the available resources and the network topology location. Information regarding the API Endpoints in the operator's gateway and credentials are required for this interaction. This interface can be used to provision communication services for newly deployed applications or to steer and request information or changes to existing communications.
- **Applications:** The management applications lifecycle from onboarding to un-deployment is a key feature of the CORC. Applications are onboarded to the CORC using a specific information model to be developed that provides a detailed characterization of each of the components that form the application, including information regarding requirements and where to find the necessary artefacts (such as images), information about the topological connections between components with links characterized by performance requirements and references to the application endpoints where users will be accessing the applications. The orchestrator will make an interpretation of this information and make the necessary coordinated requests to the domain orchestrator of the

clusters in each zone required to realize the instantiation of the application as well as to the operator gateway to create the connections between the zones. During the execution of the instance, the control loops in the CORC will monitor the metrics provided by the infrastructure, verify the match with the application definition and perform requests to the different providers to correct the deployments.

The control loops that observe the compliance of the deployment with the deployment are serious candidates to benefit from the use of AI/ML algorithms that can assist the decision making based on the information obtained from the metrics. This is supported by the inclusion of an AI/ML framework for MLOps in the platform that can help automate the management of the ML pipelines lifecycle and help deploy the trained models and run its services within the orchestrator.

8 Solution validation

The objective of the industrial scenario is to develop a realistic, advanced and business-relevant innovative use case for Industry 4.0 (I4.0), specifically focusing on assessing and verifying the performance and functionalities of the Cloud-Continuum ORChestrator (CORC) solution to be developed within the 6GSMART project.

The industrial scenario to verify the service orchestration solution supported by a 6G network will be simulated in a laboratory context, and it covers a pharmaceutical production facility, more specifically various clean rooms, where the environment needs to be controlled to minimize contamination risks, with strict and regular cleaning and hygiene measures to keep them in a suitable condition for use. In addition to maintaining a clean atmosphere, clean room-specific machinery needs to be protected from vibration and kept within certain limits of lighting, temperature, pressure and humidity. All these key aspects must be adapted to each process so that they do not adversely affect the processes, which could ruin the production of an entire manufacturing production batch.

As they are an essential part of the production process and will determine compliance with the quality requirements of the product and its chemical components, the flow and preservation of raw materials, and the proper use of containers and packaging must all adhere to clear guidelines in this type of environment. Because of this, robots are used for automating various processes, supplying the right amount of material at the right time for production and packaging.

Critical industrial environments, as described above, require continuous monitoring to ensure smooth operations, optimize efficiency and prevent any potential problems that may arise. With the advent of 6G technologies and their characteristics, such as ultra-high-speed, ultra-reliable, and low-latency connectivity, together with the concept of the extreme edge, a new paradigm for plant monitoring is emerging that will impact the industrial landscape.

The **extreme edge** means deploying computing and data processing capabilities as close as possible to the data source, ensuring real-time decision-making and less reliance on centralized infrastructure. This helps manufacturers monitor changes in machine functionality before failure and mitigate them before they become more serious, as well as changes in environmental conditions that can influence the quality of the final product. Sensors can track changes and transmit them to edge nodes for real-time processing and analysis in real-time to avoid disruptions in plant operation.

By leveraging the features of 5G advance/ 6G and edge technologies, the clean room monitoring system achieves unprecedented levels of efficiency, responsiveness and adaptability. Key benefits include:

- **Real-time Monitoring:** With 6G ultra-high-speed connectivity, the industrial plant monitoring system can collect vast amounts of data from multiple machines, sensors and devices distributed throughout the clean room in real-time. These sensors capture information such as temperature, humidity, vibration, and other relevant parameters, ensuring a comprehensive view and status of the plant's operations.

- **Low Latency and High Reliability:** 6G's low-latency communication ensures minimal delay between data acquisition and analysis. This enables real-time decision-making and rapid response to any anomalies or critical events within the plant. Additionally, the high reliability of 6G networks guarantees uninterrupted data transmission, reducing the risk of data loss or downtime.
- **Edge Computing at the extreme edge:** By deploying edge computing resources at the extreme edge of the network, the plant monitoring system can process and analyse data locally, closer to the data source. This minimizes the need for sending data to a centralized cloud infrastructure for processing, resulting in reduced latency and improved overall system performance.
- **Autonomous Decision-Making:** The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms at the extreme edge enables autonomous decision-making capabilities within the plant monitoring system. By analysing real-time data and comparing it against historical patterns and predefined thresholds, the system can automatically trigger actions or alerts in response to deviations or critical events. This reduces the need for manual intervention, speeds up response times, and enhances overall operational efficiency. This proactive approach helps minimize downtime and optimize maintenance schedules, leading to cost savings and increased plant efficiency.
- **Enhanced Safety and Risk Mitigation:** With real-time monitoring, immediate alerts, and autonomous decision-making, the plant monitoring system enhances safety and risk mitigation. It can quickly identify potential safety hazards, abnormal conditions, or equipment failures, triggering appropriate actions or alarms. This ensures quality and minimizes the potential impact of incidents on the environment.

Overall, the use of 6G technologies and the extreme edge in the monitoring of industrial plants, and in this case clean rooms, improves the way industrial operations are managed. It enables real-time, data-driven decision-making, predictive maintenance and improved safety, ultimately leading to optimized plant performance, increased efficiency and reduced downtime.

The ultimate goal of the proposed industrial scenario is to minimize human intervention and errors while enhancing productivity. The proposed solution aims to connect new machines with the existing manufacturing machines in a clean room machine pool in a flexible way. The idea is to have a seamlessly integration process with the existing network of machines, improving the traditional method where manual work and time-consuming efforts are required to connect new machines to the network. By centralizing the machines onto a single platform, the solution enables monitoring of data from all machines from a single location, streamlining operations and improving efficiency.

The following figure shows the initial draft of the proposed cloud-edge based IoT architecture for the industrial use case, with an edge computing layer for offloading computation. On the left of the picture, different objects in the clean room such as sensors, machines, equipment, IoT devices, etc. are connected via networking. The IoT devices located in the clean room are regarded as extreme edge computers because they are beside the production equipment and machines for data acquisition and processing. These IoT devices have different specifications and are small devices typically resource-constrained and cannot perform data or computing-intensive tasks (e.g., Arduino, Raspberry Pi, and Up Board).

Figure 8. High level architecture of the Industrial pilot.

Thus, they can offload their more intensive workloads to other types of edge computing resources, in this case to the edge servers which are high-end servers at the edge of the network near IoT devices. The edge servers have much more resources than IoT devices or user devices. Therefore, they can be used to perform more data or computing-intensive workloads, such as data aggregation, intensive data processing, as well as store a great amount of data and perform highly complex workloads to offload the IoT. On the other hand, some workloads that edge servers cannot afford to process can be offloaded to remote Cloud.

The architecture envisages two initial network services:

- **Machine Interconnection Network Service (MINS):** MINS is deployed on each manufacturing machine within the clean room machine pool. Its primary function is to collect data from the sensors present on each machine and translate this data into a standardized messaging format. By doing so, MINS gathers data from every machine/device and forwards it to the Factory Edge Network Service (FENS) for local processing and storage. MINS connects each machine with the clean room machine pool's network.
- **Factory Edge Network Service (FENS):** FENS is deployed at factory level and acts as a local processing and storage unit for the data collected by MINS from individual machines. Moreover, FENS is responsible for connecting each machine in the clean room machine pool to create an interconnected network. If there are multiple factories worldwide, each factory will have its FENS, and these will be connected to a central server. Therefore, The FENS facilitates data collection from each machine in the clean room, and it also connects the clean room with other clean rooms. Consequently, data from multiple clean rooms can be exchanged, allowing for seamless coordination across different manufacturing facilities.

FENS is also connected to a remote cloud. The data from FENS is transmitted to the cloud server for long-term storage and processing. Then, when a new machine is brought into clean room, the Cloud-Continuum ORChestrator (CORC) will be responsible for provisioning and configure the necessary software and for integrating it into the corresponding network service. This smart manufacturing architecture can integrate every machine with the rest of the machines in the clean room smoothly and quickly.

The scenario envisages real-time monitoring, based on the collection of data from multiple sources:

- Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs), giving access to various inputs and outputs, used to control and monitor industrial equipment. We will communicate with them by means of the OPC-UA protocol.
- Machinery sensorisation, including vibration, pressure, temperature, and humidity. Collected from sensors strategically placed on machines involved in critical processes of drug production.
- Sensors for monitoring environmental conditions by means of ambient light, humidity and temperature and distributed evenly throughout the clean room.
- Robots in charge of supplying the production line and it is necessary to have their position and verify that they are in their place of operation and have not deviated from their trajectory.

9 Summary and conclusions

This document includes the results of the project task *6GSMART-SP1-L2-T2.1.2: Revisión del estado del arte y principios de diseño de redes público-privadas, bajo la perspectiva de un desarrollador de tecnologías cloud* described in the project's execution plan.

Current ecosystem that makes possible the leveraging of an integrated cloud-continuum with the characteristics that allow reaching the goals in terms of performance, data privacy and cost-effectiveness demands architectures, tools and mechanisms that enable the integration between public and private clouds. This can be achieved by adequate management and orchestration systems like the CORC, that enable the distribution of loads across a cloud-continuum that expands across these domains.

Telco operators play an important role in the creation of an interconnection fabric that glues together these domains. Initiatives like the GSMA Operator Platform aim to establish an interface point at which developers and enterprises can access the resources offered by the operators.

The high-level architecture presented in D1.1 contains specific requirements and design principles that are particular to enable this integration across domains and they have highlighted in this document. In the last section of this document a solution validation use case has been introduced and it will be developed and detailed in further deliverables according to the project work plan to validated the CORC management and orchestration solution.

